

MEDICAL SCIENCES

PRIMARY IMMUNE DEFICIENCY IN PATIENTS WITH MEFV GENE MUTATION

Nasrullayeva G.,

Azerbaijan Medical University, Scientific-Research Laboratory of Immunology

Mollayeva N.,

Azerbaijan Medical University, Department of Children's Diseases I

Mammadova V.,

Azerbaijan Medical University, Scientific-Research Laboratory of Immunology

Namazova B.

Azerbaijan Medical University, Department of Children's Diseases I

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Introduction:

Primary Immune Deficiencies (PIDs) are a group of rare genetic disorders that affect the immune system. As these are congenital conditions, patients with PIDs are more susceptible to viral, bacterial, and fungal infections, as well as autoimmune diseases and malignancies. The rapid advancement of immunological science in recent years has led to the identification of over 450 gene mutations causing PIDs (19). This has enabled a gradual increase in diagnosed cases in accordance with the modern PID classification. As new gene mutations are discovered, classifications are revised. For instance, an updated classification was presented in 2021, following the 2020 IUIS (International Union of Immunologic Societies) classification, as 26 new monogenic mutations were identified (20). According to ESID (European Society for Immunodeficiencies), the majority of PIDs are antibody-based immune deficiencies, accounting for 50.7% of all cases (11).

Literature data suggest that multiple gene mutations can coexist in a patient with PIDs. However, clinical symptoms are typically associated with a single underlying gene mutation. For instance, the characteristic symptoms of ataxia-telangiectasia—such as unsteady gait, recurrent bronchopulmonary diseases, and intellectual impairment—are attributable to a mutation in the ATM gene (1, 21).

Familial Mediterranean fever (FMF) is a genetically inherited monogenic autoinflammatory disease that predominantly affects Armenian, Turkish, Jewish, and Arab populations (2, 8, 25). The disease results from a mutation in the MEFV gene, located on the short arm of chromosome 16. FMF is often a familial pathology, with 50% of patients reporting a family history of the disease.

Statistical studies indicate considerable variations in the prevalence of this disease across different countries. It is believed to be most prevalent in Turkey, especially in the Anatolia region, where the incidence rate is between 1:400 and 1:1000. In 2022, Turkey is expected to have 27,504 FMF patients. Armenia is the next most affected country, with a disease prevalence of 1:500, which implies over 6000 FMF patients in a population of 3 million. In Israel, the disease prevalence is 1:1000 (10,000 FMF patients in a population of 7 million). Iran has a lower prevalence of 1:20,000, and

in 2020, 4,256 cases were registered in Iran out of a population of 88 million. In other countries, the disease is found among the aforementioned ethnic groups, possibly due to global population migration (2, 3, 5, 8). The exact number of FMF patients in Azerbaijan is unknown; however, it is estimated that there could be between 8,000 and 10,000 cases in a population of 10 million.

FMF characterized by recurrent fevers and serous inflammatory attacks, which can occur at any age but primarily begin during school years. The disease, caused by mutations in the MEFV gene, manifests as recurrent high fevers of 39-40 degrees Celsius, abdominal pain, serositis, joint symptoms, peritonitis, erythema on the skin, mouth ulcers, pharyngitis, and kidney complications. Abdominal pain usually starts in a specific area and then spreads throughout the abdomen—a symptom seen in 95% of patients. Periods of spontaneous remission can last for months or even years. The course of the disease can sometimes be atypical; in such cases, a diagnosis can be confirmed through the detection of MEFV gene mutation. The MEFV gene consists of 10 exons, and over 370 mutational variants have been identified to date (4, 5, 18, 25).

Two primary phenotypes of FMF are recognized:

- Type I FMF is characterized by fever, joint pain and swelling, skin rash, and severe abdominal pain. Episodes typically last 2-3 days and can occur several times a month or as infrequently as once a year. During these episodes, increased levels of erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR), leukocytosis, and fibrinogen are observed in the blood. Progressive amyloidosis can also develop as the disease progresses.

- Type II FMF is characterized by the development of amyloidosis without any preceding clinical signs (22).

Approximately 25% of individuals clinically diagnosed with FMF carry only one pathogenic gene variant, and 10-20% carry no pathogenic gene variant. In cases where the patient's genetic mutation cannot be identified, the diagnosis of FMF is made based on characteristic clinical signs. This does not exclude the diagnosis of FMF. About 75% of typical FMF cases in Turkish, Arab, Jewish, and Armenian populations are primarily caused by five mutations: V726A, M694V,

M694I, M680I, and E148Q. Of these, M694V is the most common mutation, with prevalence ranging from 20% to 65% in different populations. However, individuals carrying the mutant gene sometimes exhibit no clinical symptoms and are considered carriers (4, 5, 10, 18, 22, 25).

Colchicine is the gold standard for treating FMF. In addition to suppressing inflammation, it also prevents the onset of amyloidosis. If a patient does not respond favorably to colchicine therapy (in 5-10% of cases), alternative treatments such as anti-IL-1 therapy, anakinra, riloncept, or canakinumab are prescribed (18).

Objective: The aim of this study is to identify and analyze the occurrence of MEFV gene mutations that coexist with mutations causing immune deficiency.

Materials: From 2010 to 2023, 160 patients with primary immune deficiency diseases were registered at the Scientific-Immunology Laboratory and Pediatric Department of Azerbaijan Medical University. MEFV gene mutations were detected in three of these patients: one boy and two girls. In two patients with MEFV gene mutations, agammaglobulinemia, was confirmed, and in another patient, ataxia-telangiectasia was confirmed.

Methods: Patients underwent clinical and laboratory examinations, which included general and biochemical, serological, and immunological blood analyses. The immune system examination involved phenotyping of immune competent cells (CD3+, CD4+, CD8+, CD19+, CD16/56+, HLA DR) by flow cytometry. Serum levels of IgM, IgG, IgA, IgE, INF- γ , and IL-4 cytokines were determined using the ELISA method, and the phagocytic activity of neutrophils was determined using the NBT method. Patients also underwent lung X-rays, chest CT scans, ultrasound examinations of lymph nodes and abdominal organs, and genetic analysis at the "Invitae" laboratory (USA). PID diagnoses were confirmed in patients through a Primary Immune Deficiency panel that included 429 genes (12, 13).

Discussion of Results: All the studied patients had anamnestic and clinical symptoms typical for PID. These included cases of consanguinity and child death in the family, recurrent infections of the bronchopulmonary, gastrointestinal, skin and mucous membranes in the patients, failure of traditional therapy, and gradual retardation. Different MEFV mutations were detected in three (2%) of the 153 patients with PID: M694V gene in one patient, M680I in another, and an A744S pathogenic mutation in the third patient (Table 1).

Table 1. Genetic mutations and primary clinical symptoms of PID patients with MEFV mutations.

P	PID diagnosis	PID gene	MEFV gene	Clinical symptoms	Recurrent fever	Abdominal syndrome	Joint syndrome
1	Bruton syndrome	BTK	M680I	Skin inflame	No	No	Yes
2	Agammaglobulinemia	TRNT1	A744S	ARI, pneumonia, bronchitis, otitis	Yes	3-4 times per year	No
3	Louis-Bar syndrome	ATM	M694V	Sinusitis, arthritis, diarrhea	No	No	Yes

Agammaglobulinemia - type I - Bruton Disease is associated with low or complete absence of one or more classes of immunoglobulins, as well as B-lymphocytes. At this time, no pathology is observed in the maturation of T lymphocytes and their amount in the peripheral blood. In such patients, frequent repeated bacterial infections, chronic course and complications are found (6, 9). In our observation, congenital agammaglobulinemia was diagnosed in 2 patients with MEFV mutation. One of them had type I - X-linked agammaglobulinemia (XLA). A mutation in the BTK gene (Bruton tyrosine kinase) on the X chromosome was discovered

and the disease was named Bruton syndrome. The disease is familial, it is observed in boys, and women are carriers (6, 16, 17, 23).

Example 1: Patient S.Z., a 9-year-old boy born of consanguineous marriage with normal height and weight. The family history revealed that the patient's two siblings were healthy, but another one boy died at the age of 1 year after pneumonia and recurrent stomatitis. The patient was breastfed for up to 6 months and his development was normal. Later, fever, pneumonia, and boils appeared on the neck and body. Staphylococcus aureus was detected in the contents of the furuncle, but the treatment only had a temporary effect.

Picture 1: Patient with Agammaglobulinemia type 1 (BTK gene mutation)

Between the ages of 2-5, he experienced numerous incidents of conjunctivitis, pneumonia, bronchitis, diarrhea, otitis, and joint pain. Hepatomegaly (+2cm), splenomegaly (+1cm) and tonsil aplasia were also noted. Pain in the joint, caries-ridden teeth, a left leg that is 2 cm shorter than the right, and large wounds and rashes on the skin of the head and body were observed (Pic. 1).

During the extensive immunological examination of the patient, it was determined that the patient lacked B-lymphocytes, as well as all classes of immunoglobulins (table 2).

Based on anamnestic data, clinical signs, and immunological analysis, the patient was diagnosed with X-linked agammaglobulinemia (XLA), type 1, also known as Bruton's syndrome. Genetic studies confirmed the pathogenic variant of the BTK c.1559G>A (p.Arg520Gln) hemizygous mutation and the pathogenic variant of the MEFV c.2040G>C (p.Met680Ile) heterozygous mutation was discovered. Although the MEFV gene mutation was detected, the patient showed no clinical signs of Familial Mediterranean Fever.

Another patient was diagnosed with type 2 autosomal recessive type of agammaglobulinemia. This type of agammaglobulinemia is caused by defects in several different genes, which are mainly associated with the formation of the pre-B cell receptor and its signaling molecules. In these cases, the differentiation of B-lymphocytes halts in the bone marrow.

Autosomal recessive agammaglobulinemia (ARA) characterized by the several following genetic defects:

- a) Defects in the μ heavy chain of intracellular cytoplasmic immunoglobulin;
- b) Defects in the $\lambda 5$ component of the light chain of the pre-B-cell receptor;
- c) Mutation of part of $Ig\alpha$ (CD79a), a component of pre-B and B-cell receptors;
- d) Mutation of $Ig\beta$ (CD79b), a part of pre-B and B-cell receptors;

e) Mutation in the BLNK gene, which encodes the B cell linker protein. This type of mutation occurs in 10-15% of cases; both boys and girls can be affected;

f) Mutation in the TRNT1 gene, located on chromosome 3 (14, 16).

The autosomal recessive TRNT1 gene mutation was first described in 2014 (15). This TRNT1 gene mutation is associated with a pathology characterized by B-cell deficiency, periodic fever, and developmental delay (SIFD - Sideroblastic anemia with B-cell immunodeficiency, periodic fevers, and developmental delay) (7, 15, 28). In 2013, Wiseman and colleagues reported a syndrome comprising congenital sideroblastic anemia, B-cell deficiency, recurrent fevers, and developmental delay in 12 children from 10 families (26). Congenital sideroblastic anemias are a heterogeneous group of hereditary diseases characterized by pathological iron deposition in the mitochondria of red blood progenitor cells in the bone marrow. Some patients also experience variable severity of hearing loss, retinal pigmentation, cataracts, hepatosplenomegaly, brittle hair, cardiomyopathy, and central nervous system abnormalities (7, 24, 27). As of 2020, 30 such patients suffering from a TRNT1 mutation, a rare form of agammaglobulinemia, have been identified (27).

Example 2: Patient A.C., a 4-year-old girl was born on time from a consanguineous marriage, with normal height and weight. Her younger brother is healthy. From the age of 1 year, the patient experienced monthly bouts of fever lasting 5-7 days, accompanied by abdominal pain and diarrhea. The patient also had bronchitis, pneumonia, stomatitis, severe anemia (Hb 78 g/l), dental caries, hepatosplenomegaly, toxic encephalopathy, and physical and mental retardation. No TORCH infections were detected in laboratory tests, and blood cultures were sterile. Amyloid A protein was higher than normal (181 mg/l, normal <6.4), and LH cells were negative.

Picture 2.

Patient with Agammaglobulinemia type 2 (TRNT1 gene mutation), exhibiting dental caries and stomatitis.

Based on clinical signs, without immune examination, the patient diagnosed with FMF and treatment initiated with Colchicine - 0.5 mg per day. However, due to the lack of effect of the treatment, the patient underwent an immunological examination, revealing an absence of B lymphocytes and all classes of immunoglobulins (table 2). Genetic analyses revealed the pathogenic variant of TRNT1 c.176_182del (p.Leu59*)

heterozygous mutation, the unknown variant of TRNT1 c.1213G>A (p.Gly405Arg) heterozygous mutation, and the pathogenic variant of MEFV c.2230G>T (p.Ala744Ser) heterozygous mutation. As a result, the patient was diagnosed with autosomal recessive agammaglobulinemia and FMF.

Table 2

Immunological indicators of patients (cellular and humoral indicators)

P	PID diagnosis	CD3 % /ml	CD4 % /ml	CD8 % /ml	CD19 % /ml	IRI	CD16/5 6 %/ml	HLA DR /ml	IgG g/l	IgM g/l	IgA g/l	IgE
1	Bruton syndrome	80/1944	41/797	37/719	0	1,1	17/413	15/364	1,0	0,1	0,2	0
2	Agammaglobulinemia	80/275	21/477	30/682	1/28	0,7	17/483	16/455	0,5	0,3	0,2	0
3	Louis-Bar syndrome	65/1281	37/473	25/320	16/315	1,4	26/512	11/216	10,0 IVIG	8,3	0	0

ATM gene mutation is an autosomal recessive gene defect that causes Ataxia-telangiectasia-AT (Louis-Bar syndrome), a very severe variant of PID. AT is a multisystem disease that causes both cellular and humoral deficits, as well as cerebral ataxia, telangiectasias in the eyes and skin. Patients primarily suffer from persistent infectious diseases, metabolic disorders, and are highly prone to malignancy. Children who appear healthy at birth develop normally until they are 2-3 years old. After that, they start showing symptoms of cerebellar ataxia, mental and physical development stops or even regresses, gradual expansion of scleral vessels, telangiectasia, eyeball tremor - nystagmus, and bulbar conjunctivitis. Areas of hypo- and hyperpigmentation appear on the skin and have a "milky coffee"

color. (1, 21). Severe bronchopulmonary infections, sinusitis, otitis and stomatitis repeated in patients. In adolescence, patients develop bronchiectasis, respiratory and cardiovascular insufficiency, and malignancies.

Example 3: Patient N.N, an 8-year-old girl, was born out of a consanguineous marriage. Her older brother is healthy. She developed normally for the first 2-3 years of life. Later, she experienced repeated infections of the bronchus-lung, ear-nose-throat (ENT) organs, and the gastrointestinal system. Gradual cerebellar ataxia, stopping of mental and physical development, and the appearance of telangiectasias were observed in the patient. As the disease progressed, the patient's mobility was impaired, and speech defects formed.

Picture 3: Patient with irregular teeth and telangiectasia in the eyes.

The level of alpha-fetoprotein from the laboratory parameters was significantly higher than normal. As the patient's age increased, the amount of alpha-fetoprotein also increased. Serum IgA level was 0%, IgG was 5-6 g/l before starting replacement therapy with IVIG. Among the immunological indicators, the amount of IgM was significantly high (table 2).

Genetic studies confirmed the pathogenic variant of the homozygous mutation between exons 4-22 in the ATM gene and the pathogenic variant of the heterozygous mutation MEFV c.2080A>G (p.Met694Val). Although the MEFV gene was detected, the patient had no clinical signs of Familial Mediterranean Fever.

Conclusion:

The presence of recurrent fever, abdominal pain, serositis and peritonitis in patients may suggest a diagnosis of Familial Mediterranean Fever based solely on family history and clinical symptoms. However, a more precise diagnosis can be made when the MEFV gene mutation is identified. In certain cases, if treatment with Colchicine is ineffective, it may indicate underlying congenital immunodeficiency in these patients. Detailed family medical histories, coupled with instrumental, laboratory, immunological, and genetic analyses, assist in making an accurate diagnosis and implementing targeted treatments for patients. Moreover, the mutation of the MEFV gene can sometimes be detected incidentally in PID patients who do not exhibit symptoms of Familial Mediterranean Fever.

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References:

1. Aguado J., Gómez-Inclán C., Leeson H. et al., The hallmarks of aging in Ataxia-Telangiectasia // *Ageing Res Rev* 2022 Aug;79:101653. doi: 10.1016/j.arr.2022.101653.
2. Alibakhshi R., Mohammadi A., Ghadiri K., et al., Spectrum of MEFV gene mutations in 4,256 familial Mediterranean fever patients from Iran: a comprehensive systematic review // *Egyptian Journal of Medical Human Genetics* volume 23, Article number: 5 (2022), Open Access Published: 18 January 2022
3. Ben-Chetrit E., Touitou I., Familial mediterranean fever in the world. *Arthritis Care Res* (2009), 61(10):1447–1453
<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/epdf/10.1002/art.24458>
4. Bhatt H., Cascella M. Familial Mediterranean Fever // National library of medicine. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK560754/>
5. Bilge SY., Sari İ., Solmaz D., Şenel S., Em-mungil H., The distribution of MEFV mutations in Turkish FMF patients: multicenter study representing results of Anatolia. *Turkish Journal of Medical Sciences*.2019;49: p.472–477.
6. Bonilla FA., et al., Practice parameter for the diagnosis and management of primary immunodeficiency // *J Allergy ClinImmunol*, Nov. 2015, volume 136, number 5
7. Chakraborty PK., Klaus Schmitz-Abe K., Kennedy EK. et al., Mutations in TRNT1 cause congenital sideroblastic anemia with immunodeficiency, fevers, and developmental delay (SIFD) // *Blood*. 2014 Oct 30; 124(18): 2867–2871.
8. Govindaraj GM., Jain A. et al., Clinical, immunological and genomic characteristics of children with X-linked agammaglobulinemia from Kerala, South India // *Human Immunology* Volume 83, Issue 4, April 2022, Pages 335-345

9. Dundar M., Fahrioglu U., Yildiz SH. Et al., Clinical and molecular evaluation of MEFV gene variants in the Turkish population: a study by the National Genetics Consortium // *FunctIntegr Genomics* 2022 Jun;22(3):291-315
10. Grossman C, Kassel Y, Livneh A, Ben-Zvi I. Familial Mediterranean fever (FMF) phenotype in patients homozygous to the MEFV M694V mutation. // *Eur J Med Genet* 2019; 62:103532.
11. <https://cci-reporting.uniklinik-freiburg.de/#/> ESID Registry Network Reporting Tool public webpage
12. [https://www.invitae.com/en/providers/test-catalog/gene-20844?tab=Diagnostic \(MEFV\)](https://www.invitae.com/en/providers/test-catalog/gene-20844?tab=Diagnostic+(MEFV))
13. [https://www.invitae.com/en/providers/test-catalog/gene-21357 \(TRNT1\)](https://www.invitae.com/en/providers/test-catalog/gene-21357+(TRNT1))
14. [https://www.omim.org/entry/616959 \(TRNT 1 gene mutation\)](https://www.omim.org/entry/616959+(TRNT+1+gene+mutation))
15. Mendonca LO., Prado AI., et al., Case Report: Expanding Clinical, Immunological and Genetic Findings in Sideroblastic Anemia With Immunodeficiency, Fevers and Development Delay (SIFD) Syndrome // *Front. Immunol.*, 14 April 2021
16. Nasrullayeva G, Mammadova V., Khalilova A., Shahgeldiyeva Sh., The Novel Patient with BLNK Gene Type of Agammaglobulinemia // *Open Access Library Journal* 2017, Volume 4, e4114, ISSN Online: 2333-9721, ISSN Print: 2333-9705
17. O'Toole D., Groth D., Wright H., et al., X-Linked Agammaglobulinemia: Infection Frequency and Infection-Related Mortality in the USIDNET Registry // *Journal of Clinical Immunology* volume 42, pages 827–836 (2022)
18. Ozturk K., Coskuner T., Baglan E. et al., Real-Life data from the largest Padiatric Familial Mediterranean fever cohort // *Front. Pediatric*, 20 January 2022, *Sec. Pediatric Rheumatology*.
19. Quinn J., Vicki Modell V., Orange J., Modell F. Growth in diagnosis and treatment of primary immunodeficiency within the global Jeffrey Modell Centers Network // *Allergy, Asthma & Clinical Immunology*, volume 18, Article number: 19 (2022)
20. Redmond M., Scherzer R., Prince B., Novel Genetic Discoveries in Primary Immunodeficiency Disorders // *Clinical Reviews in Allergy & Immunology* (2022), Published: 12 January 2022
21. Sak I, Kızıllırmak D., Havlucu Y. et al., The investigated case of etiology of chylous pleural effusion: Ataxia-telangiectasia // *Tuberk Toraks* 2022 Mar; 70(1):102-106. doi: 10.5578/tt.20229912.
22. Shohat M. Familial Mediterranean Fever // *National library of medicine*.<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK1227/>
23. Takada H., Kanegane H., Nomura A., et al., Female agammaglobulinemia due to the Bruton tyrosine kinase deficiency caused by extremely skewed X-chromosome inactivation // *Blood*, 2004 Jan 1;103(1):185-7
24. Topyildiz E., Karaca N., Bas I., et al., A Novel Homozygous TRNT1 Mutation in a Child With an Early Diagnosis of Common Variable Immunodeficiency Leading to Mild Hypogammaglobulinemia and Hemolytic Anemia // *J Pediatr Hematol Oncol* 2021 Aug 1;43(6):e780-e784.
25. Van Gorp H., Huang L., Saavedra P. et al., Blood-based test for diagnosis and functional subtyping of familial Mediterranean fever. // *Ann Rheum Dis*. 2020;79(7):960. Epub 2020 Apr 20.
26. Wiseman D. H., May A., Jolles S., et al., A novel syndrome of congenital sideroblastic anemia, B-cell immunodeficiency, periodic fevers, and developmental delay (SIFD) // *Blood* 122: 112-123, 2013.
27. Yang L., Xue X., Zeng T., ChenX., et al., Novel biallelic TRNT1 mutations lead to atypical SIFD and multiple immune defects // *Genes Dis*. 2020 Mar; 7(1): 128–137.
28. Yildirim FT., Benderlioğlu E., Kaçar D., Yaralı N., A rare cause of sideroblastic anemia: TRNT1 mutation // *Consultation hematologyop* 33, Vol. 43 Issue s3, pages S28-S29, November 2021.DOI: 10.1016/j.htct.2021.10.1000